

Eco-resilient Strategies for Pest and Disease Management

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Integrated Pest and Disease Management (IPDM) is a holistic and sustainable approach aimed at controlling plant pests and diseases while minimizing dependence on synthetic pesticides. With a rising global population, sustainable agriculture is essential to achieving the Zero Hunger goal. However, increasing insecticide resistance and Modern Environmental Health Hazards (MEHs) resulting from pesticide exposure pose significant risks to both human and environmental health. IPDM offers an eco-smart solution that maintains agricultural productivity while preserving ecological integrity. This strategy integrates multiple methods - biological control, cultural practices, mechanical techniques, and the judicious use of chemicals guided by scientific monitoring and threshold-based decision-making. A cornerstone of modern IPDM is the incorporation of microbial biocontrol agents and plant growth-promoting microorganisms (PGPM), which naturally suppress pests and enhance plant immunity without leaving harmful residues.

Despite their promise, eco-friendly alternatives such as microbial bio-stimulants and biocontrol agents often show inconsistent results under field conditions, highlighting the need for deeper ecological understanding and practical validation. Moreover, over-reliance on chemical controls continues to dominate many crop protection programs, compromising the core principles of IPDM. To address these challenges, Agroecological Crop Protection is emerging as a complementary framework. It combines ecological science, farmer engagement, and landscape-level strategies to create a sustainable, socially inclusive, and environmentally resilient agricultural system.

As the urgency for sustainable farming grows, reinforcing IPDM through agroecological principles and advanced biocontrol technologies is critical to securing long-term food security and ecosystem health.

Key words: *Integrated Pest Management, Biocontrol Agents, Sustainable Agriculture, Agroecology, Plant Disease Management.*